

An Employees' Perspective of Effective Communication as a Strategy for Enhancing Organizational Performance

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Abstract

This study examines the role of effective communication as strategy for enhancing private universities performance in Jalalabad. The problem that has led to the study is differences and delays in availability of information that decreases private universities performance. The survey research methodology for this study was adopted and the study relied on primary data. The statistical population of this study was academic staff of private universities in Jalalabad. 150 sample size was determined using the random sampling technique. In fact, the result shows that flow of communication has a significant positive effects on private universities performance. More briefly, if the flow of communication is natural and smooth in an organization that would causes private universities to have an outstanding performance. Further, findings from research shows that effective communication is a cure for effective and efficient management and performance of private universities. The researcher recommends that there is a need that organization strives to communicate effectively as an integral part of the organization. Its management strategies and providing strategic solutions for storing information. It will also reduce the loss of essential information and help in minimization of organizational conflict, misunderstanding and strengthening information management.

Keywords: *Effective Communication, Nangarhar, Organization Performance*

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Introduction

An effective communication strategy is a process through which the organizational works are supported by transmitting information to each other for having better outcomes and performance. Every organization whether that is public or private they need effective communication in order to deliver their ideas, information, solutions regarding communicative problems inside the universities. It is obvious that organizations cannot be succeeded without proper communication with their employees, customers and clients. Indeed, today business market is very competitive and business is very challenging. Then, it is required to well manage all production factors of an organization and universities. Among these factors human factor is really challenging factor and it should be managed wisely. In fact, human's thoughts, emotions, and feelings should be skillfully managed to fortify highest productivity among the academic staffs of private universities.

The specialists experientially agreed and demonstrated the importance of communication during intended change. Organizational change and communication process are connected and related process. On the other hand, failure of communication causes many unfavorable outputs like low trust, job dissatisfaction, stress, and decreases in organizational commitment, division in intentions and absence (Francis & Chyke, 2016) and it can affect the efficiency of organization undesirably.

Effective communication has vital role in organizational performance and it is all because of technological change, diversification, various polices and competitiveness in the marketing place in the current time and as the businesses are expanded all over the world. In fact, organizations can make alert their employees, employers, consumers and customers about technological change, diversification, various polices and competitiveness by effective communication. Moreover, in organizations the main factor is employee's performance which can affect the whole performance of organizations. Many organizations are trying to control inner challenges and barriers which negatively affect the employees' performance. Indeed, one of the main factors of internal challenges, which negatively influence the organizational performance is effective communication (Ali, 2016).

A research was carried by Zhang & Venkatesh, (2013) by effective communication channels organizations can ensure their employees' respond, adjust, receive and improve information flow within an organization. Moreover, organizations which have strong and effective communication channels can guarantee openness, communication structure, employee feedback, adjustment to change and contribute positively to employees' performance. Effective communication is an

important factor in today's organizations for overall organizational functioning and success (Mutuku and Mathooko, 2014). Uka (2014) has figured out seven communication reasons why organizations fail to change that include insufficient communication, distrust, poor interpersonal communication skills, and conflict avoidance. Uka indicates that "research shows that up to 70 percent of change programs fail and poor internal communication is seen as the principal reason for such failure. Poor communication between organizations and employees can cause the following problems in organizations such as, losing high and key employees, decrease in motivation, frustration of employees, lack of directions, leading to confusion and misleading to purpose and performance. These factors ultimately fail organizations to achieve their goals and objectives. Statistics has shown that 90% are motivated to deliver added value who are fully informed; while those who are kept in dark almost 80% are not (The Workplace Communication Consultancy, 2005).

The following research gap is identified from the existing literature and as well as from observing the communication among academic staff in private universities. Many university disputes disagree over communications failure. The variables that are essential to communications are flow of communication, barriers to communication, effective communication and knowledge sharing. Communication is important for improving the performance of the universities. According to Rajhans (2012), communication is beyond receiving information but understanding it is feedback. Most organizational conflict has resulted due to communication failure. The same problem has been observed in private universities in Jalalabad. Further, academic staff delays in access to information seem to limit their academic performance, which can create mismanagement in the coordination of the universities activities. Therefore, the performance of employees in relation to their duties and responsibilities seem to be questioned their communication techniques in terms of performance at universities in Jalalabad. Experienced shortcomings that are not properly addressed can lead to poor performance. The research questions may guide the study and thus improving the quality of effective communication at universities in Jalalabad. This study would fulfill the above mentioned research gap. Beside this, the main objectives of the study are to examine the effect of barriers to communication on organizational performance. Secondly, to examine the effect of effectiveness of communication on organizational performance and to examine the effect of knowledge sharing on organizational Performance.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Effective Communication and Performance

Ali (2016) figured out the impact of inner communication channels on employee outputs in non-profit organization. This study is carried out in Somalia and the number of respondents were 136. The findings of this study shows that there is a positive relationship between inner communication channels and employee performance. The result of this study further shows that by effective communication in an organization employee can solve their problems they are facing with. For example, they can solve sophisticated tasks, building coordination and cooperation, and can boost up the performance of the employee. Study recommends that organizations must have effective communication with their employees this would enhance the performance of organization. Indeed, in this study the upward and down ward communication was introduced weakest communication in non-profit organizations of Somalia and further studies are recommended in this regard.

Nabi et al. (2017) examined the business communication role and effect on employee performance and job satisfaction. This research is carried about a case study on Karmasangsthan Bank Limited in Bangladesh and the number of respondents in this research were 120 respondents. This research strongly suggests that there is unquestionable positive relationship between business communication and employee's entire performance and satisfaction. This research suggested these recommendations as well. First, for the betterment of work condition some of the communication approaches should be applied. Second, upward, down ward and lateral communication should be used in the best ways in order to have great impact on performance and satisfaction of employees. Third, for making the working condition more convenient, contented and relax the managerial communication should be used in proper way. Finally, for the best work atmosphere fitting, convenient and alternate implications should be identified.

Gaither (2012) investigated the role and effect of internal communication on employee engagement. In this study secondary data were utilized for carrying out this research. The researcher collected data from 2010 to 2011 for this research paper. This research was conducted in Kosair Children Hospital (KCH). The research paper disclosed that the outcome of communication team's struggles shows a significant increase in engagement of employees for Kosair Children Hospital (KCH). Let's make it clear that there is a positive relationship between internal communication and employee engagement. The findings of this research paper further

states that enhancing and evaluating of the inner communication was the main goals of this research paper. This study recommends that take care of those interventions which can increase employee's engagement.

Florence (2015) sought the employees' performance because of communication at Ghana revenue authority, Kumasi. This research was conducted in Ghana/Africa. The number of respondents were 200. Both secondary and primary data were used for carrying out this research paper. Ordinary Least Square (OLS) estimation technique was used. The findings of this research paper indicates that there is positive relationship between employee's performance and communication. Moreover, this research paper examined at GRA the available communication system, measured employee's performance, identified the most useful channel of communication which are considered beneficial by employees and finally the failures and obstacles were also identified at GRA communication system. This paper recommends that communication flow should not only be up ward, but also it should be downward. In fact, upward and downward flow of communication can help in comprehension, smoothness of communication, compatibility, displays good behavior, produce positive output and ensures adaptability of employees to messages communicated. This paper further recommends that feedback should be highly encouraged. At last, bottlenecks communication system should be removed for enhancing the performance of employees.

Abdussamad (2015) examined the impact of communication climate on performance of the employees at government agencies in Gorontalo City (An Indonesian Case Study). This study is carried out in Indonesia. Indeed, the simple linear regression is used in this research paper. The findings of this study shows that there is a vital impact of communication climate on performance of employees at the agency of the cooperation, industry, trade, investment and small and medium enterprise of Gorontalo city. The study recommends that in the cooperation, industry, trade, investment and small and medium enterprise communication climate should be improved.

Shonubi and Akintaro (2016) figured out the effect of effective communication on performance of organization. This research was conducted in Nigeria for seeking the impact of communication on organizational performance. Indeed, secondary data was utilized from 1904 to 1914. The research paper findings show that there is positive relationship between effective communications on performance of organization. This study further states that for effective and efficient performance of organization the management should analyze the purpose of communication clearly, understand the physical and human environment

when discoursing, and proper consideration should be given to the content and tone of the message. This research paper recommends that there is need for improving the performance and the management should bring focus on making the ideas clear before communicating and best understanding of human and physical environment when communicating.

Femi (2014) inspected the influence of communication on workers' performance in selected organizations in Lagos State, Nigeria. This study was practiced in Nigeria. The data sort was primary data for this study and the number of respondents were 120. In fact, the findings of this study declares that there is relationship between communication and worker's performance and commitment. Moreover, the study shows that by effective communication reciprocal comprehension can be created between management and workers which helps both parties in building storing relationship with each other. On the other hand, the study reveals that poor communication can affect the performance of workers badly. Therefore, the research paper advises managers to speak out policies, goals and objectives for workers regularly in order to improve their performance and commitment.

Husain (2013) studied the impact of communication strategies on organizational performance: a case study of Kenya Ports Authority. This study was carried out in Kenya for finding the impact of communication strategies on organizational performance. The number of respondents were 132 and primary data was used for this study. The result of this study shows that in high-performance communication strategies has greater role because communication strategies nowadays are very common in business world, where they are used as business' plan and telling how to communicate with several business parties. Indeed, in this research paper based on findings there is positive relationship between communication strategies and organizational performance. The study suggests that for taking place effective communication barrier to communication should be rooted out and in organization the communication should flow in all directions then in this regard, concise clarity of language should be used and the receiver of communication should be attentive and pay close attention.

Ali (2016), Nabi et al. (2017), Florence (2015), Abdussamad (2015), Shonubi and Akintaro (2016), Femi (2014), Gondal and Shahbaz (2012), Husain (2013), Mutuku and Mathooko (2014), Boyaci et al. (2000), Otieno et al. (2015), Amechi et al. (2014), Angelica and Vecchio (2007), Rajhans (2012), Mayfield and Mayfield (2002), Uka (2014), Francis and Chyke (2016), Haroon (2018), Stanikzai (2017) and Tahsildari and Shahneai (2015) are also in view

that an effective communication has a significant positive effects on organizational performance .

2.2. Communication Flow and Organizational Performance

The existing of communication flow in an organization is very important because every employee will remain alert or updated according the situation. Definitely, all organizations, both private and public entities rely on some form of communication to send their messages across to their target audience, or inform their target audience of the mission and vision of their entity. When the flow of effective communication is at its ultimate employees mostly boosting their performance at the work place. For example, when the information about an organization's policies and procedures are at its optimum level with openness and accuracy; and also when the information provided is adequate, factual and has good feedback (Kacmar, Wilt, Zivnuska, and Gully, 2003).

Husain (2013) stated that it was argued that the largest beneficial resource within an entity are the employees; therefore, it is the responsibility of managers to encourage two-way flow of information to optimize organization's performance as well as employee productivity. As an organization has different types of employees and different functional parts, then there should be different types of communication flow. The flow of communication is commonly classified according to the direction of interaction: downward, upward, horizontal, diagonal, external.

2.3. Coordination/Knowledge Sharing and Organizational Performance

Communication has been widely accepted by scholars and academics as the life hood of an organization because communication is needed for exchanging information, exchanging opinions, making plans and proposals, reaching agreement, executing decisions, sending and fulfilling orders and conducting sales (Haroon, 2018). When communication stops, organized activity ceases to exist, and individual uncoordinated activities return in an organization. So, organization in an organization is a virtual as the blood of life.

2.4. Concluding Remarks

This section presents the empirical literature on employees' communication and organizational performance. To the best extent of our knowledge, the researchers only identified a significant positive effect of communication on organizational performance. The gap that identified in the literature for the existence study is following. Academic staff delays in access to information seem to limit their academic performance, which can create mismanagement in the coordination of the universities activities. Therefore, the performance of employees in relation to their duties and responsibilities seem to be questioned their communication techniques in

terms of performance at universities in Jalalabad. Experienced shortcomings that are not properly addressed can lead to poor performance. The research questions may guide the study and thus improving the quality of effective communication at universities in Jalalabad.

3. Research Methodology

a. Research Design

This research is conducted, for finding the impact of effective communication as a strategy for enhancing organizational performance. In fact, adopted questionnaires were distributed for data collection and data was collected via questionnaires. As result, the sample size was 150. The research area is the whole private universities of Jalalabad city such as, Khurasan, Al-Falah, Al-Taqawa, Spinghar and Rohan universities. The reason of selecting the universities in Jalalabd as sample is following. Academic staff delays in access to information seem to limit their academic performance, which can create mismanagement in the coordination of the universities activities. Therefore, the performance of employees in relation to their duties and responsibilities seem to be questioned their communication techniques in terms of performance at universities in Jalalabad. Experienced shortcomings that are not properly addressed can lead to poor performance. The research questions may guide the study and thus improving the quality of effective communication at universities in Jalalabad. The whole population was 360. Actually, there are different types of sampling but here the random sampling method was selected for this research. At first, data was recorded in Excel Spreadsheet and then it was converted to Eviews software and through Ordinary Least Square (OLS) the data was estimated.

b. Population

Population is the large collection of individuals or objects which is the main focus of scientific investigation. Or, population is a complete set of elements (objects or individuals) that have some common characteristics which is used by researcher in order to carry out his/her research. For example, as this research is conducted to find out the impact of effective communication on organizational performance the actual population of this research is (360) employees in different private universities in Jalalabad city.

The following table 1 represents the sample of different universities in Jalalabad City.

Table 1: Sample of Different Universities

S.No	University/ Institute	Number of Employee	of Address
1	Khurasan University	60	3 rd Phase, Jalalabad

2	Al-Falah University	80	4 th Phase, Jalalabad
3	Al-Taqwa Institute of Higher Education	55	3 rd Phase, Jalalabad
4	Spinghar Institute of Higher Education & Medical Sciences	70	2 nd Phase, Jalalabad
5	Rohan Institute of Higher Education	95	3 rd Phase, Jalalabad
Total Population		360	

c. Sampling

Sampling is a method of selecting a few individuals or objects out of the whole population to represent the entire population. For instance, the whole population's number is (360) and (150) is selected as a sample size for this study. Furthermore, there are different types of sampling technique via which one can select sample numbers out of population such as, simple random sampling, stratified sampling, systematic sampling and cluster sampling. In fact, in this study the simple random sampling was selected to select sample numbers out of population. The random sampling technique has been employed to obtain unbiased, consistent and efficient results. Table 2 provides the sample size that has selected from each university.

Table 2: Sample Size

S.No	University/ Institute	Sample Size
1	Khurasan University	30
2	Al-Falah University	35
3	Al-Taqwa Institute of Higher Education	10
4	Spinghar Institute of Higher Education & Medical Sciences	30
5	Rohan Institute of Higher Education	45
Total Sample Size		150

d. Research Instrument

Research instrument is a measurement tool such as survey, questionnaire or test which is used by the researcher in order to collect data for his/her research. In fact, for this research the questionnaire was used to collect the actual data. As far as, it is clear that questionnaire is a research device which consists of a series questions for the purpose of gathering information from respondents. There are mainly two types of questionnaires such as adopted questionnaires and constructed questionnaires. Adopted questionnaires are those questionnaires which are preexisting instrument which are useful to measure a key variable in your study. This type of questionnaire is simple and needs little effort. On the other hand, constructed questionnaire is referred to the design of a

questionnaire in which statistically useful information is gathered by researcher about given topic. As result, in this research paper the adopted questionnaires are used to gather primary data from respondents. See below table for adopted questionnaires and their authors.

Table 3: Research Instrument

S.No	Variable	Authors	Year	Number of Items
1	Communication Flow	Ali	2016	20
2	Effectiveness of Communication	Florence	2015	18
3	Barriers to Effective Communication	Boyaci et al	2000	7
4	Coordination/Knowledge Sharing	Gaither	2012	6

Source: From literature

The Cronbach’s Alpha was utilized to measure the reliability of the variables. Table 4 provides the result of Cronbach’s Alpha test. If the value of Cronbach’s Alpha is greater than 0.70, one could say that the questions developed for the corresponding variable is reliable and its vice versa. The result indicate that the value of Cronbach’s Alpha is greater than 0.70 for all corresponding variables. Thus, the questions developed for the variables are accurate and reliable.

Table 4: Cronbach’s Alpha Test for Reliability

S.No	Variable	Cronbach’s Alpha
1	Communication Flow	0.73
2	Effectiveness of Communication	0.77
3	Barriers to Effective Communication	0.75
4	Coordination/Knowledge Sharing	0.71

Source: Output generated from SPSS

e. Model Specification

$$OP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FC + \beta_2 EC + \beta_3 BC + \beta_4 NS + \varepsilon_i$$

where,

OP= Organizational Performance, β_0 = Constant/ Intercept, β_1 - β_4 = Slope Coefficients, FC= Flow of Communication, EC= Effectiveness of Communication, BC= Barriers to Communication, NS= Knowledge Sharing and ε_i = Error Terms

4. Findings and Results

a. Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistic is shown in Table 5 undertaken for the study.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of the study

Variables	Observation	Mean	St.Dev	Maximum	Minimum
FC	150	1.356	0.125	2.658	0.365
EC	150	2.365	-0.023	36.54	10.44

BC	150	0.789	0.365	40.35	8.45
KS	150	1.253	0.052	15.32	1.800
OP	150	1.368	-0.325	2.687	-0.365

Source: Data output from SPSS

Column 1 indicate the underlying variables of the study. Column 2 shows the number of observation. Column 3 indicates the average value of the variables. Column 4 shows the standard deviation from the mean value of each variable. Column 5 indicates the maximum value exist in the dataset. Finally, column 6 shows the minimum value of the data set. As, it is clear that descriptive statistics provide a short description about the dataset of the study. For example, flow of communication as an independent variable of the study has average value around 1.356 given the standard deviation 0.125. This shows the deviation of each observation from mean value on average basis. The maximum value of flow communication is 2.658 while the minimum value is 0.365. Identically, effectiveness of communication is as an independent variable of the study has average value around 2.365 which given the standard deviation -0.023. This shows the deviation of each observation from mean value on average basis. The maximum value of effectiveness of communication is 36.54 while the minimum value is 10.44. Similarly, barriers to communication is as an independent variable of the study has average value around 0.789 which given the standard deviation 0.365. This shows the deviation of each observation from mean value on average basis. The maximum value of barriers to communication is 40.35 while the minimum value is 8.45. Likewise, knowledge sharing is as an independent variable of the study has average value around 1.253 which given the standard deviation 0.052. This shows the deviation of each observation from mean value on average basis. The maximum value of knowledge sharing is 15.32 while the minimum value is 1.800. In like manner, organizational performance is as a dependent variable of the study has average value around 1.368 which given the standard deviation -0.325. This shows the deviation of each observation from mean value on average basis. The maximum value of organizational performance is 2.687 while the minimum value is -0.365.

b. Correlation Matrix

The correlation Matrix shows the co movement between the variables.

Table 6: Correlation Matrix of the study

Variables	OP	FC	EC	BC	KS
OP	1.00				
FC	0.35	1.00			
EC	0.65	0.32	1.00		
BC	0.61	0.10	0.35	1.00	

KS	0.43	0.45	0.12	0.32	1.00
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Source: Data output from SPSS

The Correlation matrix is used to show the co movement between the variables. For example, how much the organizational performance and flow of communication variables are associated to each other and in which extent they move on? The answer to this question is that organizational performance and flow of communication are positively correlated and 35 percent, both variables have co movement. In fact, the correlation coefficient of organizational performance and flow of communication is 35 percent and it is positive which suggests that both variables are moving together and they have co movement. Identically, the correlation coefficient of organizational performance and effectiveness of communication is 65 percent and it is positive which suggests that both variable are moving together and they have co movement. In the same way, Organizational performance has a positive correlation with barriers of communication. The correlation coefficient between organizational performance and barriers of communication is 61 percent and it is positive which suggests that both variables are moving together and they have co movement. Finally, Organizational performance has a positive correlation with knowledge sharing. The correlation coefficient between organizational performance and knowledge sharing is 43 percent and it is positive which suggest that both variables are moving together and have co movement.

c. Normality Test

Table 7: Normality Test

No	Variables	Skewness	Kurtosis
1	Flow of Communication	0.0032	3.003
2	Effective Communications	0.0001	3.04
3	Barriers to Communicating	0.0012	3.000
4	Knowledge Sharing	0.000	3.001

Source: Data output from SPSS

The Normality test is presented in Table 7. Normality is the assumption of OLS, which shows that the data is symmetric of corresponding variables. The data must satisfy the normality assumption in order to acquire the consistent, efficient and unbiased result. Skewness and Kurtosis tests have utilized to examine the normality. As the value of skewness test is approximately equal to zero, which indicates that the data of all variables is normal. Beside this, the value of Kurtosis test is near to 3, which clearly satisfy the normality assumption.

d. Tests for Multicollinearity

To examine the Multicollinearity problem in estimation result then it is quite important to use the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) test.

Table 8: Testing for Multicollinearity

Variables	VIF
Flow of Communication	7.23
Effective Communications	9.52
Barriers to Communicating	2.35
Knowledge Sharing	5.65

Source: Data output from SPSS

This research was selected to register multiple entries with the OLS estimate technique employed to examine the effect of effective communication on organizational performance. However, preliminary investigations are examined some important assumptions of classical liner, which might have the problem of multicollinearity. Variance inflation factor has employed to test the multicollinearity or the presence of multicollinearity. The variance inflation factor result is quoted in above table, which clearly reflect that our four independent variables are free from multicollinearity. If VIF is greater than 10 than there will be the problem of multicollinearity. As shown in above table, our four independent variables are free from multicollinearity because the value of VIF is less than 10. However, the problem of the heteroskedasticity was corrected through robust command in Eview software with a 'strong' indicator that was used in recent relationships. That automatically corrects the heteroskedasticity database. Beside this, we have also test the hetero problem through Heteroscedasticity test and the result is given.

e. Heteroscedasticity

Table 9: Testing for Heteroscedasticity

F- Statistics	0.4035	Probability	0.635
Obs * R-Squared	0.9031	Probability	0.7543

Source: Data output from SPSS

Heteroscedasticity test shows that whether the variance of the residual is same. If the variance of the residual is same, this is called homoscedasticity and the result would be efficient and consistent. If the variance of the residual is not same, this is called Heteroscedasticity and the obtained result would be inefficient and inconsistent. For this purpose, we ran a brush Godfrey-Heteroscedasticity test. The probability of this test shows that there is no Heteroscedasticity problem exists in the estimation. Thus, the obtained results are efficient and consistent.

f. Regression Result

It is quite important to estimate our models through OLS in order to obtain an efficient and consistent results of the study. The diagnostic tests would also be discussed in preceding discussions. The following table provide the regression result which is estimated through OLS.

Table 10: Regression result of the study

Variables	Coefficients	t statistic	P value
Flow of Communication	0.042	-2.50	0.002
Effective Communication	0.035	3.85	0.023
Barriers to Communication	- 0.062	-2.36	0.012
Knowledge Sharing	0.095	3.56	0.0 45
Constant	0.235	2.57	0.023
R square		0.72	
F-Statistics		36.25	
Probability		0.012	

Source: Data output from SPSS

The results of the study are presented in table 10 which was estimated via ordinary least square. The estimated coefficient of flow of communication is statistically significant and positive, which shows that in which extent the flow of communication is accessible and natural that much increases the organizational performance. Indeed, the coefficient is 0.042 given the standard error. Its significance is shown by t-statistics and probability. The statistics show that effect of flow of communication on organizational performance is statistically significant because its value is below five percent.

The estimated coefficient of effective communication is statistically significant at five percent level and it is also indicated by t statistics, which is above 2. The estimated coefficient of effective communication is 0.035. This shows that a one-unit increase in effective communication would lead organizational performance to enhance by 0.035 units. Briefly, an increase in effective communication would enhance the organizational performance due to positive relation. The estimated coefficient of barriers to communication is statistically significant at five percent level and it is also indicated by t statistics, which is above 2. The estimated coefficient of barriers to communication is 0.062. This shows that a one-unit increase in barriers to communication would lead organizational performance to decline by 0.062 units. Briefly, an increase in barriers to communication would decline the organizational performance due to positive relation. The estimated coefficient of knowledge sharing is statistically significant at five percent level and it is also indicated by t statistics, which is above 2. The estimated coefficient of knowledge is 0.095. This shows that a one-unit

increase in knowledge sharing would lead organizational performance to enhance by 0.095 units. Briefly, an increase in knowledge sharing would enhance the organizational performance due to positive relation.

The R-Square of the study shows the variation of explanatory variables of the study. The R-square of the study is 0.72 which shows that 72 percent of the variation in the dependent variable is due to independent variables of the study. The F-statistics shows the significance of overall model of the study. The probability of F-Statistics is below five percent and that is the significant level.

5. Discussion

This comparative study aimed to focus on the relationship between effective communication and organizational performance. The study carried on the private universities in Jalalabad-Nangarhar. The OLS estimation technique was utilized to obtain the result of the study. The dependent variable for the study is organizational performance. Independent variables of the study are flow of communication, barriers to communication and etc. The questionnaire was selected according to the purpose of the study. Linear regression was used to find out the impact of communication on the universities performance.

The findings of this study show that there is a significant relationship between effective communication and universities performance. Communication is crucial in any type of organization. Private or Public success depends on effective communication and timely information flow to lead employees to perform their duties in a proper way. Universities top management must create the communication process is an integral part of management strategy because it has a direct effect in achieving universities goals. Employees need to have a general sense of what to do, the role of effective communication in the office and how to help in their function. Employees feel confident when their ideas are received by senior top management - This can encourage a sense of creativity and passion in the office. Communication techniques are crucial for better understanding and easy movement needed information. This study shows that employees prefer certain types of communication methods at every level of management. Email communication cannot be effective for field staff who have limited access to the internet. While it is useful for certain situations, where employees could reach to internet with ease. So, it depends on the context of each Universities. The management of the organization must understand the proper way of communicating them. As a result, effective communication makes the dorsal bone productive and stable for

universities. Employee involvement in the organization is very important to the organization and can effectively promote its organizational performance.

It was concluded that independent variable had a significant impact on the dependent variable (organizational performance) on private sector universities. Boyaci et al. (2000) research confirmed the findings of the present study. The study examined the impact of communication strategies on organizational performance. The study concludes that open communication is effective for performance. Other studies that support the result of the current study are by Mayfield and Mayfield (2002), Uka (2014), Francis and Chyke (2016), Haroon (2018), Stanikzai (2017) and Tahsildari and Shahneai (2015). The findings of the present study examined the impact of employee communications on organization performance. It is recommended that effective organizational communication strategies need to be developed by sharing information inside and outside the organization that works and finally would lead the universities to improve their performance.

6. Conclusion

This research paper examined the effective communication as a strategy for enhancing organizational performance and this research was conducted on private universities of Jalalabad City for finding the effect of communication on organizational performance. Indeed, in this research paper the Ordinary Least Square regression was used to estimate its results and adopted questionnaires were used for data collection and the sort of data was primary data. The results show that there is a positive relationship between effective communication and organizational performance.

In fact, the results show that the flow of communication has a positive relationship with organizational performance. For example, if the flow of communication is natural and smooth in an organization that causes good organizational performance and when the communication is effective then employees effectively do their tasks which causes organizational performance. Moreover, if in an organization the barriers to communication are rooted out then employees will perform their tasks without doubt and hesitation which causes the organizational performance. On the other hand, knowledge sharing which has a vital role in an organization when there is the habit of sharing knowledge among employees definitely they become very alert which causes the organizational performance because the employee will share the knowledge what they have with one another. All in all, if an organization wants to have the best organizational performance then it should focus on an effective communication system.

7. Recommendations

Following is the recommendations for private universities to enhance their performance by eliminating the barriers of communications.

1. First, try your best as a manager of an organization to have good climate for flow of communication. Indeed, if an organization has natural flow of communication system each and every thing goes smoothly and naturally that leads an organization to high organizational performance.
2. Second, try to have effective communication system in organizations because effectiveness has vital role in high organizational performance, for example, if your information to employees is not on time. Then, it does not have any effect on employees.
3. Third, as a manager all the barriers and obstacles should be rooted out in organization because the existence of barriers and obstacle threatens the organizational performance because the barriers directly influence employees when employees are influenced definitely they become passive and slow and they cannot do their tasks openly that directly influence the organizational performance that leads organization to failure.
4. Finally, as a manger of an organization should make the learning organization where each and everybody can learn and share knowledge with others that leads an organization to its high organization performance. By sharing knowledge all employees become alert and active and they understand polices, information, rules and they can easily exchange their ideas openly for the betterment of organization.

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